

METHODOLOGIES OF GEOLOGICAL SCIENCE.

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Annotation. Any field of science, along with the subject of research, is armed with general and special methods of its study. A method is a method and ways of conducting research, an approach aimed at studying existence. Scientific laws are general and important aspects of phenomena, rules about their internal regularities. The science of basic methods and principles of knowledge is called methodology. This term has a second meaning, which is interpreted as teaching about the system of scientific methods. Among other sciences, geology also has its own methodology. Methodology (which includes "metageology" and the like as a subject of geology and an object of study) is of great importance among the theoretical foundations of science. Geological methods retain their level of importance in the perspective of science, but we will limit ourselves to the description of preliminary notes during our reflections.

Main part. One of the general manifestations of the method of knowledge is materialistic dialectics (the application of rules about the generality of interactions between phenomena in nature and their dialectical development). Two important methods - comparative and historical methods ensure the clear manifestation of materialistic dialectic (Kedrov B.M., 1967). First, let's consider the comparative method. The origin of knowledge is known from life experiences. Let's look at some of its consequences. At the heart of knowledge is always the comparison of phenomena. Using comparison, a person strives from the obvious to the invisible, from the known to the unknown, from the simple to the complex. A person cannot "invent" anything that has not been similar before: what he knows is only a slightly more complicated version of that thing that was previously mastered by consciousness. Man only compares and expands the field of knowledge through the difference between the

simple and the complex. Sometimes it seems that in the study of the macrocosm, the method of comparison is not used, and knowledge about "mysterious" objects is directly acquired (for example, in the study of spatial bodies, there is no "primary", i.e., simple object for comparison). However, the similarity of the structure of the atom to the solar system, the ideas about "wave-particle" are the results of comparing the known with the unknown. In our next example, we will witness the creation of a new physical representation from the combination of two "known" models. Although we use the abstraction characteristic of mathematics in the methods of comparison, here we are referring to sciences that have the status of historicity. A specialist in the field of geology studies the modern world in depth by comparison. If he tries to study the past by means of the method of comparison through the modern world, this is now actualism or the actualist method. Actualism is one of the scientific methods of geology. It is used in the reconstruction of the geological past related to the future by using the results of the study of modern phenomena. However, the method of comparison remains the main method of actualism. However, actualism alone is not enough to study the past. Historical or comparative-historical methods widely used in historical sciences are of great importance. This method is a generalization of comparative and historical methods. The essence of the comparative-historical method is manifested in the comparative study of events in time and space: similarities and differences, heredities and innovations, interdependences are clarified. From this it becomes clear that actualism is an independent part of the comparative-historical method. Also, experimental and modeling methods and traditional methods unique to geology are widely used in geology.. Here we will consider the self-modeling method. This method is based on accepting one of the natural or technical phenomena as a natural model of the geological process. Self-modeling has been used from the early stages of geological development to the present day (Vysosky B.P., 1973). As we noted above, this is one of the forms of a systematic approach to the study of phenomena.

Literature:

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